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Registration and Evaluation Management Information System in the CIT-Eds. Inc.

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Abstract: A web-based program called the Registration and Evaluation Management System (REMS) was developed for CIT Educational Development System Inc. Based on the gathered data, the management handled 200 to 400 students in weekly training sessions, which led to challenges in managing students and affected their manual strategy for recording student information, performance, and payments. This often resulted in misplaced records and a lack of transparency in evaluating student performance and payments. The study focused on automating a variety of tasks carried out by the CIT Director, teachers, staff members, and students. The components of REMS include Teacher Evaluation, Admin Reports, and Online or On-Site Student Registration. The portal allows students to select courses, determine their schedules, and upload payment receipts through several payment centers, such as MLhuillier and Palawan Express. Teachers, on the other hand, may use the system to assess students' outputs for various course sessions by providing grades and comments for evaluation. The system can also generate various reports, including the list of students by session, payments made, and TESDA voucher qualification. Through ViaNet, an Application Programming Intelligence (API), the system is able to produce and deliver SMS notifications regarding a student's registration status. The project aligns with Sustainable Development Goals with the following SDG's The selected Sustainable Development Goals include SDG 5: Gender Equality, SDG 8: Decent Work and Economic Growth, SDG 9: Industry, Innovation, and Infrastructure, SDG 11: Sustainable Cities and Communities, SDG 12: Responsible Consumption and Production, and SDG 17: Partnerships for the Goals. Based on the SUS results from alpha and beta testing, the system achieved good performance with an average score of over 80%. The system that was implemented in the company ensured that every field was checked and validated to avoid invalid entries and errors. It also contributed to the training centers by assisting in student registration, session evaluation, student performance monitoring, and file management procedures.

Keywords: Sustainable Development Goals, Online Registration, Walk-in Registration, Payment Method, Evaluation Method, System Usability Scale, Modified Waterfall Methodology.

1. Introduction

The training center was organized by CIT to sustain its quality marketing and educational learning through its qualified learners with efficient facilities. The Computer Information Technology Educational Development System (CITEDS) is a leading company that offers training programs for students, indigents, and professionals across in Zamboanga Region IX. The training center provides advanced learning education in the field of information technology (IT) through direct hands-on activity using a variety of applications like Adobe Photoshop CS6, CC, Adobe Flash CS6, and Internet Browsing with paid trainers and teachers to enhance the capabilities and expertise of individuals in the field of computers. This training facility, which has been operating in Zamboanga City for more than ten years, is still in operation today. The CITEDS was founded on July 6, 2012, and manage by the program director, owned and operated the company. The training center's interim location is the Southern City Colleges (Central Campus) Building on Pilar Street in Zamboanga City, Philippines. This training center operates every weekend (Saturday and Sunday), and all enrolled trainees from various schools, universities, colleges, and agencies are present on that day.

As a result, many trainees are daytime employees and students from public schools nearby in the city. These are the only days when management and itemized students are accessible to perform the training session. This training facility is officially affiliated with the government and is backed by several departments thanks to its legal school certification from Southern City Colleges, DTI Permit Certification, and DepEd Certification. The solution includes a portal where students may log in and view crucial data including session scheduling and their accounts. In order to provide updates on classes or training, it also helped with news feeds to improve student communication during registration and payment updates, the suggested solution will also use an API. The

students and staff of Zamboanga City's public and private businesses, organizations, institutions of higher learning, and agencies can also use the planned system online. The proposed strategy has also been used to evaluate student performance for the 2D Animation NC III training sessions with improved solutions and specific features. The database for the administrators, instructors, and students will also benefit the suggested system, allowing them to quickly find accurate records depending on their permission to view the data.

1.1 General Objectives

The main objective of the is to develop a web-based system for “Registration and Evaluation Management Information System in the CIT Educational Development System Inc.”

1.2 Specific Objectives

The specific objectives of this research are to develop a module via which students may register and enroll in the system online:

1. Develop a module that the student will register online and allows the administrator to register walk-in students on the system, then the system will automatically send SMS notifications when the admin approves the student registration and payment procedure.
2. Design a module that allows administrators to upload student schedules of classes or sessions to the system and enables the teacher to manage student classes depending on the sessions attended.
3. Integrate a module that the students can change the payment mode or by submitting official receipt of either Palawan, M Lhullier in .pdf,.jpeg, and.png formats online.
4. Evaluate the students’ performance using evaluation module based from the 15 sessions through grading input.
5. Create a module that allows the student to upload files for MS Word, Excel, PowerPoint, photoshop like jpg, png, psd format, and Adobe Flash like fla, swf, mov, wav, gif format onto the system. To develop a module that allows teachers to handle 2D animation core evaluations based on the TESDA Self-Assessment Guide by choosing remarks.
6. Generate daily, weekly, monthly, and yearly reports on student registration, payment, and evaluation data, list of competent students following the teacher's evaluation of the 2D cores training, and TESDA Vouchers aligned with the 2D Animation NC III.

Fig 1. shows a Use Case Diagram with three (3) users, namely the student, instructor, and administrator, as well as their responsibilities and duties in the system. The three users are claimed to be notably different in their roles and duties in this diagram, where there are constraints and limitations on traversing the system represented by an arrow toward the list or functions of the system in the middle.

1.3 Scope and Limitation

The researcher presented a solution for the CIT Educational Development System Inc., where the suggested system includes a module where the administrator may make updates so that students can access and read the announcements generated by management. Because the admin is the system's end user, the management can only publish certain notices or events. This project is a web-based system that can automatically register students online. Furthermore, the management can register the walk-in student. The system will allow the administrator to view and authorize registered enrollees, as well as a database where the administrator can access their student data and information, namely their payments and sessions or subjects to be taken. After the registration and approval procedure, the system contains an API module that can automatically produce a notice in the form of a short message and send it to the enrollee's mobile phone number. The SMS notification or API module, on the other hand, is exclusively designed for the student side following admin registration approval.

The system may create reports that list student payments and topic records based on the date specified, but only the administrator has access to these. Furthermore, the suggested system would take complete payment by submitting receipts in .pdf, .png, and .jpeg formats online. The system is a module that generates a yearly statistical approach of registered pupils. The system has a feature for recording all operations and service activities, which will be restored in the historical phase to protect the data and references. Because the system features an evaluation module to record each performance, symbolizing a check mark, only the instructor can assess their students' performances based on the submitted files aligned to the 15 sessions and TESDA cores for 2D animation. In the review process, the proposed system lacks an Artificial Intelligence (AI) function. The instructor cannot enter grades in the grading phase if the student did not submit any files for sessions 1-15, and the teacher cannot pick notes if the student did not upload any files for 2D animation cores training exercises.

The suggested system would not function without an internet connection for online registration and enrollee enrollment. Enrollees who fail to process owing to a fluctuation in internet connection will be automatically rejected by the system and will not be saved in the system. The only user who can register walk-in students is the administrator. The enrollee has no authority to authorize their own registration. Thus, they must wait for admin permission. Furthermore, the student cannot produce system reports of their sessions attended and payments because only the administrator has permission to maintain and retrieve their information. The system is not linked to the employee's wage or other features of services provided by other organizations or agencies. This system cannot function without the required hardware and software versions. Users should be given a username and password for the verification procedure when they login to the system.

2. Review of Related Works

From the gathered review and related literature, review related studies, including of related journals and books, the researcher will be capable in providing some ideas to commit the management data and information for the CIT Educational Development System Inc. in the field of their operations and other services over cloud computing.

The researcher highlighted and emphasized the need to create and develop a Web-based system using available alternative solutions using PHP, JavaScript, jQuery, Apache and MySQL (Singh, Kaur, H., & Gupta, O. P., 2016). It also utilizes the Cascading Style Sheets, Ajax application, XML tool and in addition to this, the system will also be shaped by HTML 5 methods and basics 2b HTML with applied Bootstrap scheme (Barrett, D. J., et al., 1999). Through this articles and journals references it will give some ideas for managing documents and automated forms. As a result, the researcher will utilize an automated system to assist a large amount of data. The system will apply API solutions to generate SMS notification to identify the student registration and confirmation of the admin. The system will use an alternative solution for the student attendances which is based on the sessions attended in a sense of the student appearances (O. Olaleye, A., et al., 2013).

The researcher will apply an automated recording for teacher evaluation that will assist the evaluation process of the student performances for the 15 sessions uploaded files and 2D animation cores aligned to the TESDA self-assessment guide accredited from 2D animation NC III. This alternative solution is applied to generate student performances which are validated and rated by the admin over the internet. Thorough assessment of proposals the research will be an essential management and planning tool to make a user-friendly evaluation system that will facilitate student outputs, then the teacher will provide feedback and necessary information to improve targeting and efficiency of the student productivity. Under the references of journals, the researcher will utilize statistical methods using bar graph scale to identify the number of the student population and the standard economic growth of the company based on the student population and their payments with applied forecasting method. As a utility tool the research will cater the Portable Document Format (PDF) upon which the user will generate the system to support every detail of the content for the student record and accounts and other summary reports. The following references the researcher will identify the usefulness of the Management Information System (MIS) that will be navigated with the three users, specifically the admin or the front desk, students and teachers with their separated modules, roles and functions. The proponents also decided to develop an Automated Payment System to assist the payments of the student based on their sessions and classes attended where paid in the form of uploaded receipts done online (Meng, S., et al., 2009)

3. Methodology

The system's updated Waterfall Model is shown in Figure 2.1, which also discusses the specifics of this section. The study used this methodology, which makes it simple to pinpoint the typical risk associated with business services. Utilizing this approach has a number of benefits, including its design flexibility, which enables adjustments to be made at various points throughout the project (Eason, O. K., 2016). The system development process involves breaking apart a complex system into smaller units that will make it simpler to produce data and do cost estimates for CITEDS, the system's intended end user.

Fig. 3 shows a Waterfall Model was used on the system development, which is represented its phases as follows: requirements gathering and analysis, system design, implementation, testing, and deployment system.

3.1 Requirements Gathering and Analysis

In this phase, where after obtaining permission in conducting this study, the researcher will manage a survey questionnaire to obtain the respondents assessment. The researcher will collect some necessary information that is needed throughout survey using some related questions regarding to the company environment particular in the part of registration and evaluation process. The researcher will also take some review related works as a guide for some recommendations that are necessary to work with to provide better solution and alternatives tools. At the same time, the researcher will applying some accurate methods and techniques in order to solve the risks of the CITEDS management. In this phase, the developer will assemble the following users: admin, students and teacher to assist all the data on the database system as a bases on collecting and retrieving information of the student details and their payments.

3.1.1. An interview and ocular observation were conducted to assess the performance of the system with regards to the registration procedures and keeping of students records and its payments. To notify the student approval the registration module will requires a cellphone number to be fill-out during the registration for the validity of the student registration and sessions payments.

3.1.2. After the development of the proposed management information system the respondents assessed its reusability, maintainability, security, usefulness and functionality, and evaluation on the system appeal.

3.2 Users and Characteristics

- Admin – is the main user to maintain the system and have an access to manage (save, update, delete) and generate each enrollee, subjects, payments, and TESDA Voucher throughout the system particular in the registration of the enrollees or students.
- Students – are the registered trainee that was approved by the admin. A user that can monitor its account and records status over the internet.
- Teachers – are the teaching staff for 1-15 sessions training and the registered trainer for 2D Animation which authorized and approved by the admin. A teacher that can monitor and evaluate the student’s performances based on the core provided stated in the qualification.

3.3 Architectural Design

Data Flow Diagram Level 1

Fig. 4 shows the DFD 1 for online student registration and the admin approval data flow diagram.

Fig. 5 shows DFD 1 for the student online payment and admin validation of the student payment data flow diagram.

Fig. 6 shows the DFD 1 for the student-uploaded session file and teacher evaluation data flow diagram.

Fig. 7 shows the admin manages walk-in student registration and payment data flow diagram.

3.4 System Design

Fig. 8 shows the registration dashboard.

Fig. 9 shows the student registration form dashboard.

Fig. 10 shows the student request for approval dashboard.

Fig. 12 shows the student payment dashboard.

Fig. 13 shows the adding session schedule for students.

Fig. 14 shows the added dashboard.

admin session

Fig. 16 shows the teacher evaluation dashboard for the student core activity file uploaded.

Fig. 17 shows the admin generates a report dashboard with t-test statistical inferential analysis.

Fig. 18 shows the admin generates reports for the student list with session payment, qualified students for training, competent students in training, grade history, training rate history, scheduling history, online payment history, walk-in payment history, and scholarship grant list.

3.5 Testing

The researcher utilized the System Usability Scale (SUS) questionnaire to conduct a survey of CITEDS members who have the ability and skills for this project. The researcher conducted Alpha Testing for the IT Experts and Beta Testing for the CIT Administrator and Staff, Students and Teachers. The result is show in the graph below. The SUS Questionnaire is generally used after the respondent had an opportunity to use the system being evaluated but before any discussion takes place. Respondents should be asked to respond to each item, rather than thinking about items for a long time. All items should be checked. If a respondent feels that he/she can't respond to a particular item, he/she should mark the center point of the scale (Lewis, J. R., 2018).

Table 1 SUS score from IT Expert

Table 1 shows a graph of a SUS score above that explains that out of 4 respondents from the IT Expert they were tested and navigated by the following Department Dean of Computer Science, Engineering and Information Technology in different Universities represented with respondent 1 from Zamboanga State of Polytechnic University, respondent 2 from Southern City Colleges Inc., respondent 3 from J.H. Cerilles State College and respondent 4 from Zamboanga State of Polytechnic University. Where the R1 scored 50%, the R2 scored 100%, R3 scored 90% and R4 scored 90%. To summarize all their scores, it will generate an average score of 89.06%. According to the scheme of SUS, the Registration and Evaluation Management Information System in the CIT Educational Development System Inc. has an excellent performance, and there were 2 respondents who commented and suggested the system functions.

Table 2 SUS score from CIT Administrator

Table 2 above explains that out of 4 respondents from the CIT Administrator and Staff, R1 scored 82.5%, and both R2, R3, and R4 scored 87.5%. To summarize all their scores, it will generate an average score of 90.9%. According to the scheme of SUS, the

Registration and Evaluation Management Information System in the CIT Educational Development System Inc. has an excellent performance, and they did not comment on the system functions.

Table 3 SUS score from CIT Students

Table 3 shown above, explains that out of 10 respondents from the students, where the R1 has scored 77.5%, the R3 gave 87.5%. To summarize all their scores, it will generate an average score of 90.9%. Furthermore, R5, R6, R7, and R8 all obtained a uniform score of 92.5%, indicating a consistently high level of satisfaction with the system’s usability. Meanwhile, R2 and R9 scored slightly lower with 82.5%, while R10 provided the lowest score of 50%, suggesting concerns or difficulties encountered with the system. According to the scheme of SUS, the Registration and Evaluation Management Information System in the CIT Educational Development System Inc. has an excellent performance, and they found out some difficulties on the system functions. Despite this outlier, the overall mean score remains within the “Excellent” range based on SUS interpretation. This demonstrates that the majority of the respondents perceived the system as efficient, user-friendly, and highly functional in addressing the needs of the institution.

Table 4 SUS score from CIT Teachers

Table 4 above explains the 4 respondents from the Teachers with their scores based on the rating scheme of the project system, where R1 scored 100%, R2 scored 87.5%, R3 scored 90%, and R4 scored 72.5%. To summarize all their scores, it will generate an average score of 68.75%. According to the scheme of SUS, the system has a good performance where only 1 respondent shared his expression on the system functions, and the rest of the respondents didn’t comment on the system functions.

3.6 Implementation

In this section, the researcher implemented the proposed system in the CITEDS company, allowing the end-users to access and utilize the management system over the internet. The installation of the system followed several procedures to ensure proper implementation and to identify different software and hardware constraints. This phase also revealed other challenges of the system after reviewing each prototype, particularly in algorithm analysis, which required debugging or modifications in some features and functions not aligned with their services. Moreover, the system design was examined to

determine its suitability for the business processes, especially in terms of service prototypes, forms, colors, fonts, and overall concepts.

3.7 Deployment System

In this phase, the researcher delivered the system to the CIT Educational Development System Inc., which approved it through the agreement between the admission office and the developer. The system was provided with the necessary installer and drivers. At this stage, the developer also issued an acceptance certificate, indicating the provision and authority for the CIT Educational Development System Inc. to utilize the system.

4. Discussion

Based on the Alpha testing result of the from four (4) respondents where the SUS generated average scores is 89.06%. According to the scheme of SUS that the system was in an excellent performance and only 2 respondents who commented for the purpose of clarification understanding of the system on the system. Where according to respondent stated that the system should improve the validations particular the contact number and to make sure it will only accept the correct format for the system for as to be efficient and other respondent emphasized that the system is highly recommended to implement in the company where make sure to check the validation rule in every field to avoid invalid entry or error accordingly.

In the Beta Testing, the system was tested and navigated by the CIT Staff of the training center. To summarized all their scores where it will generate an average score of 90.9%. According to the scheme of SUS that the Registration and Evaluation Management Information System in the CIT Educational Development System Inc. has an excellent performance and they didn't comment the system function. Based from the result of beta testing from the CIT Students and to summarized all their scores where it will generate an average score of 87.5%. According to the scheme of SUS that the system has an excellent performance and they don't have any comments on the system functions. Lastly, the result for beta testing from the CIT Teachers where to summarized all their scores it will generate an average score of 68.75%. According to the scheme of SUS that the Registration and Evaluation Management Information System in the CIT Educational Development System Inc. has a good performance where only 1 respondent who shared his expression on the system functions and the rest of the respondents, they didn't comment the system functions.

To generalize all the comments and suggestions on the Alpha Testing and Beta Testing here are the recommendation based on the findings and conclusions of the study to be considered which decided that the system is highly recommended to implement in the company where make sure to check and validate the rule in every field to avoid invalid entry or error and hopefully this project system will contribute to the training centers that will assist in their student registration and student session files evaluation procedures.

5. Conclusion

During the development of the project system, the researcher realized the difficulty of understanding the common problems that remained unresolved in the training center, particularly their manual practices in student registration and payment. There were also many considerations that the researcher had to balance between system development and the documentation phase.

To summarize the comments and suggestions from both Alpha and Beta Testing, the study concluded that the system is highly recommended for implementation in the company, with particular attention to checking and validating rules in every field to avoid invalid entries or errors. It is also expected that this project system will contribute to

training centers by assisting in student registration, session evaluation, performance monitoring, and file management procedures.

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